

Microwave assisted improved synthesis of 6-carbethoxy-5-aryl-3-(2-thienyl)-2-cyclohexenones using inorganic solid support and their antibacterial activities

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Abstract : An efficient one-pot synthesis of 6-carbethoxy-5-aryl-3-(2-thienyl)-2-cyclohexenones (4a-g) has been achieved by the cyclocondensation of (2E)-1-(2-thienyl)-3-aryl-2-propenones (1) with ethyl acetoacetate (EAA) under microwave irradiation (MWI) using inorganic solid support. The synthesis highlights a comparative study of microwave and conventional techniques and catalytic role of various inorganic support used. All the products have been characterized by IR, ¹H NMR and MS study and screened for their antibacterial activity.

Keywords : Microwave, cyclohexenones, Michael addition, inorganic support, antibacterial activity.

Introduction

The chemistry of cyclohexenone derivatives continues to draw the attention of synthetic organic chemists due to their varied biological and pharmacological activities¹. Further, cyclohexenones are efficient synthons in building heterocyclic compounds such as indazoles^{2,3} or fused heterocycles such as benzoselenadiazoles and benzothiadiazoles⁴, benzopyrazoles and benzoisoxazoles^{5,6} or carbazole⁷ derivatives. Microwave irradiation has emerged as a convenient non-conventional energy source in diverse synthetic transformations⁸⁻¹⁴ with significant rate accelerations, higher yield under milder conditions and high product purity, ease of manipulation and environment-friendly reaction conditions. The reactions are generally carried out in open vessels using polar solvent as energy transfer media or solvent free condition using neat reactant or solid support. The effect of microwave irradiation in chemical reaction is a combination of the thermal and non-thermal effects¹⁵.

Results and discussion

Conventional methods¹⁶ for the synthesis of cyclohexenone involve longer reaction time, toxic sol-

vents and lower yields. In view of eco-friendliness of solventless approach under microwaves (MW), the biopotential of cyclohexenones and our ongoing program¹⁷ towards green synthesis, we herein report a facile one-pot rapid synthesis of 6-carbethoxy-5-aryl-3-(2-thienyl)-2-cyclohexenones (4a-g) on various solid supports under microwave irradiation (MWI). Conventional synthesis is also reported for comparison. The reaction of (2E)-1-(2-thienyl)-3-aryl-2-propenones (1a-g) with ethyl acetoacetate (2) in presence of anhydrous K₂CO₃ (method B) or basic alumina with catalytic amount of piperidine (1 to 2 mL) (method C) under microwave irradiation and conventionally (method A) resulted desired 6-carbethoxy-5-aryl-3-(2-thienyl)-2-cyclohexenones (4a-g) (Scheme 1). The reactions under both microwave irradiated methods (B and C) were simple, rapid, clear and efficient in comparison to conventional method (A). Both the procedures (B and C) gave higher yield in comparison to conventional method (A). The product in method (B) is formed in comparatively lower yield and purity as compared to method (C).

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Scheme 1. Reagents : (A) anhy. K_2CO_3 /acetone/room temperature, (B) anhy. K_2CO_3 /MWI and (C) basic alumina/piperidine/MWI.

Best result in terms of yield and reaction time was obtained with method (C) (Table 1). These solid supports have advantages over the conventional solution phase reac-

Table 1. Comparison of reaction time and yield of compounds (4a-g)

Compd.	Ar	Method-A	Method-B	Method-C
		a (h)/b	a (min)/b	a (min)/b
4a	4-Methoxyphenyl	14/51	5/71	3/94
4b	3-Methoxyphenyl	14/60	4/79	3/90
4c	3,4,5-Trimethoxyphenyl	17/48	6/73	3/93
4d	4-Chlorophenyl	14/57	7/76	5/96
4e	4-Hydroxyphenyl	15/49	7/67	4/85
4f	4-Dimethylaminophenyl	16/45	8/69	6/88
4g	3-Nitrophenyl	15/54	5/72	3/85

a = Time and b = Yield (%).

tions because of the good dispersion of active reagent sites, associated selectivity and easier workup. Thus in the presence of base, thieryl containing chalcone ana-

logues (1) and ethyl acetoacetate (2) produce intermediate Michael adduct (3) which in turn after intramolecular cyclocondensation of the methyl group originating from acetoacetic ester and the ketone function of the initial chalcone resulted cyclohexenones (4a-g) (Scheme 1). The cyclocondensation of ethyl acetoacetate with chalcones leads to the generation of two chiral centers at C-5 and C-6 in the structure of cyclohexenones (4a-g). As the explored reaction is not stereoselective, both configurations of the chiral carbon atoms are expected to be noticed in the synthesized cyclohexenones (4a-g), which would result in a mixture of diastereomers. No attempt to separate the diastereomeric cyclohexenones has been undertaken, and the cyclocondensation products have been characterized in the form of the mixture originated from the synthesis.

Structural analysis of the newly synthesized cyclohexenones (4a-g) comprised IR, 1H NMR and mass spectral investigations. The IR spectra of these compounds revealed a sharp strong absorption band above 1700 cm^{-1} that can be correlated with the presence of the ester function in the structure of cyclohexenones (4a-g) which did not respond to $FeCl_3$ test. Furthermore, another sharp strong absorption band was noticed at approximately 1660 cm^{-1} and was assigned to the carbonyl group conjugated with a carbon-carbon double bond, thus excluding the intermediate Michael adduct having an extra carbonyl group. The 1H NMR spectra substantiated the results of the IR analysis. The absence of singlet around $\delta 2.0$ (due to CH_3CO moiety) confirmed the formation of (4a-g) instead of the Michael adduct (3). The characteristic signals of an ethyl ester moiety (a triplet around $\delta 1.0$ and a quartet around $\delta 4.0$) confirmed the presence of the ester group in the structure of cyclohexenones (4a-g). The proton at C-5 as a multiplet approximately around $\delta 3.0$ and C-6 proton signals around $\delta 3.15$ appeared as pairs of doublets. The two diastereotopic protons at C-4 of the cyclohexenone ring were represented in the 1H NMR spectra of compounds (4a-g) as a multiplet around $\delta 2.1-2.4$. A singlet of the vinylic proton at C-2 of the cyclohexenone ring that appeared at approximately $\delta 6.5$

confirms that the intramolecular cyclocondensation subsequent to the Michael addition actually took place. The assignment of the protons in the thiophene ring at approximately δ 7.10, 7.50 and 8.20 and the number of the other aromatic protons of the aryl substituent on C-5 of the cyclohexenone ring was always in good agreement with the assigned structure (4a-g).

Finally, in order to check the possible intervention of 'specific (non-thermal) microwave effects', the results obtained under microwave were compared to conventional heating. The final temperature was measured at the end of microwave irradiation by introducing a glass thermometer in the reaction mixture in the flask. In the case of compound 4a the reaction was carried out using a pre-heated oil bath under the same reaction conditions (time, temperature and vessel) for 5 min at 85 °C for method B and for 3 min at 122 °C for method C. It was found that the reaction did not occur and the reactants remained unchanged in both the methods, thus suggesting that the effects of microwave is not purely thermal and can be related to the effect of the support as they behave as poorly heating conductors where as they are strong absorbent of electromagnetic field¹⁸.

Antibacterial activity :

All the synthesized compounds (4a-g) were screened for their *in vitro* antibacterial activity at concn. of 200 μ g/mL in DMF against Gram-positive *S. aureus*, *S. fecalis* and Gram-negative *P. mirabilis* and *P. aeruginosa* bacteria by the paper disc diffusion method. The zone of inhibition was measured in mm. Standard drugs Amicacin and Amoxyclav for Gram-positive and Tobramycin and Amoxycillin for Gram-negative bacteria were used as reference compounds. The zone of inhibition was compared with the standard drugs after 24 h of incubation at 25 °C. All the compounds (4a-g) exhibited moderate to good activity against the test organisms. The activity of compound (4c) having 4-hydroxyl substituted phenyl at C-5 in cyclohexenone ring was found most potent against *S. aureus* and *P. aeruginosa* among the seven compounds screened and was comparable to activities of standard drugs. The results are summarized in Table 2.

Table 2. Antibacterial activity of compounds (4a-g) (zone of inhibition in mm)

Compd. and standard drugs	Gram-positive bacteria		Gram-negative bacteria	
	<i>S. aureus</i>	<i>S. fecalis</i>	<i>P. mirabilis</i>	<i>P. aeruginosa</i>
4a	11	27	20	20
4b	15	20	15	25
4c	28	15	25	28
4d	22	27	28	27
4e	30	18	28	31
4f	20	22	22	15
4g	13	27	11	27
Amicacin	35	38	-	-
Amoxyclav	33	32	-	-
Tobramycin	-	-	38	34
Amoxycillin	-	-	38	35

Conclusion :

The proposed microwave-assisted methodology on inorganic solid supports provides an easier facile practically convenient and eco-friendly one-pot synthesis of potentially bioactive cyclohexenones (4a-g) in comparison to existing conventional methods. Significant antibacterial activity was observed with compound 4e against *S. aureus* and *P. aeruginosa*.

Experimental

All the melting points are uncorrected and were recorded using open-end capillaries. Thin layer chromatography of synthesised compounds was performed on silica gel-G plates using benzene-ethyl acetate (9 : 1) solvent system and iodine as visualising agent. The IR spectra were recorded on DIGILAB FTS-14 or Perkin-Elmer 157P spectrophotometer in KBr (ν_{\max} in cm^{-1}). ¹H NMR was recorded on CDCl₃ on a Varian CFT-20 or Bruker DRX-300 (300 MHz) spectrometer using TMS as internal standard (chemical shifts in δ ppm). FAB mass spectra were recorded on Jeol SX-102 spectrometer. All compounds gave satisfactory elemental analysis and spectral data. All the reactions were carried out in a domestic microwave oven (Kenstar, output energy 1200 W, frequency 2450 MHz, Model No. MO9706).

General procedure of 6-carbomethoxy-5-aryl-3-(2-thienyl)-2-cyclohexenones (4a-g) :

Synthesis of (2E)-1-(2-thienyl)-3-aryl-2-propenones (1a-g) was performed using 2-acetyl thiophene and sub-

tituted aromatic aldehydes using basic alumina under microwave irradiation as reported^{17a}.

Method (A) :

Conventional solution phase¹⁶ :

To a solution of chalcone 1 (0.1 mol) in acetone (35 ml) was added ethyl acetoacetate (0.15 mol) and anhydrous K_2CO_3 (0.4 mol). The reaction mixture was stirred for 2–3 h and kept for over-night at room temperature. The mixture was filtered and the filtrate on concentration under reduced pressure gave a solid, which on crystallisation from ethanol afforded analytical samples of compounds (4a–g).

Method (B) :

One pot solid phase MWI (anhydrous K_2CO_3) :

To a solution of chalcone 1 (0.1 mol) in acetone (10–20 mL) was added ethyl acetoacetate (0.15 mol) and anhydrous K_2CO_3 (4.0 g). The mixture was uniformly mixed with a glass rod and air dried to remove the solvent. Adsorbed mass was irradiated in a microwave oven (35% microwave power) for a period specified as in Table 1. After the completion of reaction (TLC), the reaction mixture was cooled at room temperature and product was extracted with ethanol (2 × 20 mL). Removal of the solvent under reduced pressure and subsequent recrystallisation with ethanol resulted compounds (4a–g).

Method (C) :

One pot solid phase MWI (basic alumina and piperidine) :

A mixture of chalcone 1 (0.01 mol), ethyl acetoacetate (0.02 mol) and piperidine (1–2 mL) was dissolved in ethanol (5–10 mL) and taken in a 100 ml borosil flask. To this basic alumina (4.0 g) was added and the reactants were properly mixed with the help of a glass rod. Adsorbed material was dried in air and irradiated inside the microwave oven at medium power level (50%) for a period specified as in Table 1. On completion of reaction (TLC), the mixture was cooled at room temperature and worked up as described in method B.

The compounds synthesized by the above procedure were in agreement with those obtained by methods (A) and (B) on the basis of their m.p., mixed m.p. and IR spectra. The characterization data of synthesized compounds (4a–g) are given below.

Compound (4a) : Yellow crystals, m.p. 90 °C (Found : C, 67.26; H, 5.54. Calcd. for $C_{20}H_{20}O_4S$ (356) : C, 67.39; H, 5.66%); δ_H ($CDCl_3$, ppm) : 1.31 (3H, t, $-OCH_2-CH_3$), 2.15–2.43 (2H, m, 4- H_α and 4- H_β), 3.67 (1H, m, 6-H), 3.76 (1H, dd, 5-H), 3.83 (3H, s, $-OCH_3$), 4.23 (2H, q, $-OCH_2-CH_3$), 6.45 (1H, s, 2-H), 6.93–7.42 (m, broad and unresolved, Ar-H), 7.57–8.18 (3H, m, Ar-H, thiophene); ν_{max} (KBr, cm^{-1}) : 3110 (aromatic C–H), 2928, 2835 (aliphatic C–H), 1732 ($\nu C=O$ ester), 1656 ($\nu C=O$ ketone), 1596, 1511 (C=C); m/z : 357 ($M+1$), 356 (M^+), 342, 327, 311, 283, 282, 273, 267, 255, 243, 231, 161, 121, 107.

Compound (4b) : Yellow crystals, m.p. 93 °C (lit. ^{16a} 90–91 °C) (Found : C, 67.28; H, 5.57. Calcd. for $C_{20}H_{20}O_4S$ (356) : C, 67.39; H, 5.66%); δ_H ($CDCl_3$, ppm) : 1.31 (3H, t, $-OCH_2-CH_3$), 2.14–2.46 (2H, m, 4- H_α and 4- H_β), 3.63 (1H, m, 6-H), 3.72 (1H, dd, 5-H), 3.90 (3H, s, $-OCH_3$), 4.26 (2H, q, $-OCH_2-CH_3$), 6.41 (1H, s, 2-H), 6.87–8.22 (m, broad and unresolved, Ar-H), 7.57–8.19 (3H, m, Ar-H, thiophene); ν_{max} (KBr, cm^{-1}) : 3102 (aromatic C–H), 2929, 2852 (aliphatic C–H), 1732 ($\nu C=O$ ester), 1656 ($\nu C=O$ ketone), 1594, 1517 (C=C); m/z : 357 ($M+1$), 356 (M^+), 342, 327, 311, 283, 282, 273, 267, 255, 243, 231, 161, 121, 107.

Compound (4c) : Yellow crystals, m.p. 164 °C (lit. ^{16a} 164–165 °C) (Found : C, 63.37; H, 5.74. Calcd. for $C_{22}H_{24}O_6S$ (416) : C, 63.44; H, 5.81%); δ_H ($CDCl_3$, ppm) : 1.33 (3H, t, $-OCH_2-CH_3$), 2.14–2.40 (2H, m, 4- H_α and 4- H_β), 3.64 (1H, m, 6-H), 3.70 (1H, dd, 5-H), 3.83 (3 × 3H, s, 3 × $-OCH_3$), 4.24 (2H, q, $-OCH_2-CH_3$), 6.46 (1H, s, 2-H), 6.63–6.71 (m, broad and unresolved, Ar-H), 7.51–8.14 (3H, m, Ar-H, thiophene); ν_{max} (KBr, cm^{-1}) : 3087 (aromatic C–H), 2934, 2837 (aliphatic C–H), 1731 ($\nu C=O$ ester), 1646 ($\nu C=O$ ketone), 1591, 1509 (C=C); m/z : 416 (M^+), 401, 387, 386, 371, 341, 323, 278, 250, 236, 231, 121, 107, 95, 83.

Compound (4d) : Yellow crystals, m.p. 147 °C (Found : C, 63.16; H, 4.61. Calcd. for $C_{19}H_{17}ClO_3S$ (361) : C, 63.24; H, 4.75%); δ_H ($CDCl_3$, ppm) : 1.37 (3H, t, $-OCH_2-CH_3$), 2.12–2.42 (2H, m, 4- H_α and 4- H_β), 3.66 (1H, m, 6-H), 3.74 (1H, dd, 5-H), 4.21 (2H, q, $-OCH_2-CH_3$), 6.41 (1H, s, 2-H), 7.23–7.40 (m, broad and unresolved, Ar-H), 7.57–8.16 (3H, m, Ar-H, thiophene); ν_{max} (KBr, cm^{-1}) : 3112 (aromatic C–H), 2977 (aliphatic C–

H), 1735 ($\nu_{\text{C=O}}$ ester), 1653 ($\nu_{\text{C=O}}$ ketone), 1592, 1491 (C=C); m/z : 363 ($\text{M}+2$), 361 (M^+), 345, 315, 287, 285, 249, 203, 165, 163, 111.

Compound (4e): Yellow crystals, m.p. 172 °C (Found: C, 66.49; H, 5.26. Calcd. for $\text{C}_{19}\text{H}_{18}\text{O}_4\text{S}$ (342): C, 66.65; H, 5.30%); δ_{H} (CDCl_3 , ppm): 1.32 (3H, t, $-\text{OCH}_2-\text{CH}_3$), 2.14–2.43 (2H, m, 4- H_{α} and 4- H_{β}), 3.64 (1H, m, 6-H), 3.69 (1H, dd, 5-H), 4.26 (2H, q, $-\text{OCH}_2-\text{CH}_3$), 6.47 (1H, s, 2-H), 6.61–7.30 (m, broad and unresolved, Ar-H), 7.59–8.12 (3H, m, Ar-H, thiophene), 9.42 (1H, s, -OH); ν_{max} (KBr, cm^{-1}): 3424 (OH), 3086 (aromatic C-H), 2920, 2851 (aliphatic C-H), 1740 ($\nu_{\text{C=O}}$ ester), 1658 ($\nu_{\text{C=O}}$ ketone), 1593, 1529 (C=C); m/z : 343 ($\text{M}+1$), 342 (M^+), 327, 313, 297, 269, 268, 241, 224, 120, 107.

Compound (4f): Orange crystals, m.p. 138 °C (Found: C, 68.11; H, 6.16. Calcd. for $\text{C}_{21}\text{H}_{23}\text{NO}_3\text{S}$ (369): C, 68.27; H, 6.27%); δ_{H} (CDCl_3 , ppm): 1.33 (3H, t, $-\text{OCH}_2-\text{CH}_3$), 2.17–2.45 (2H, m, 4- H_{α} and 4- H_{β}), 3.06 (2 \times 3H, s, $\text{N}(\text{CH}_3)_2$), 3.62 (1H, m, 6-H), 3.70 (1H, dd, 5-H), 4.23 (2H, q, $-\text{OCH}_2-\text{CH}_3$), 6.47 (1H, s, 2-H), 6.68–7.13 (m, broad and unresolved, Ar-H), 7.52–8.19 (3H, m, Ar-H, thiophene); ν_{max} (KBr, cm^{-1}): 3105 (aromatic C-H), 2921, 2849 (aliphatic C-H), 1736 ($\nu_{\text{C=O}}$ ester), 1658 ($\nu_{\text{C=O}}$ ketone), 1595 (C=C); m/z : 369 (M^+), 354, 339, 325, 324, 321, 310, 296, 280, 252, 251, 249, 233, 221, 219, 107, 95, 83.

Compound (4g): Yellow crystals, m.p. 150 °C (Found: C, 61.34; H, 4.53. Calcd. for $\text{C}_{19}\text{H}_{17}\text{NO}_5\text{S}$ (371): C, 61.44; H, 4.61%); δ_{H} (CDCl_3 , ppm): 1.35 (3H, t, $-\text{OCH}_2-\text{CH}_3$), 2.14–2.40 (2H, m, 4- H_{α} and 4- H_{β}), 3.61 (1H, m, 6-H), 3.72 (1H, dd, 5-H), 4.20 (2H, q, $-\text{OCH}_2-\text{CH}_3$), 6.41 (1H, s, 2-H), 7.57–8.18 (3H, m, Ar-H, thiophene), 7.67–8.25 (m, broad and unresolved, Ar-H); ν_{max} (KBr, cm^{-1}): 3100 (aromatic C-H), 2920, 2851 (aliphatic C-H), 1740 ($\nu_{\text{C=O}}$ ester), 1655 ($\nu_{\text{C=O}}$ ketone), 1593 (C=C), 1529, 1350 (NO_2); m/z : 371 (M^+), 356, 351, 342, 341, 325, 324, 313, 299, 296, 273, 259, 223, 222, 198, 197, 107.

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